

TOWARDS NEW DELIVERY MODELS FOR FUTURE CAP- TOOLS4CAP PROJECT

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Introduction

Tools4CAP is a Horizon Europe project (Call: Horizon-CL6-2022-Governance-01; Type of Action: Horizon-CSA) that brings together 20 partners from 18 EU countries. The period during which the project is being carried out is 2023-2026. The European Union (EU) has formally adopted the reform on the new Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) for the period 2023-2027, which establishes the New Delivery Model (NDM). The New Delivery Model comes with significant changes in the CAP decision-making and governance processes, including the re-arrangement of responsibilities among the EU and Member States (MSs). Moreover, following the European Commission CAP proposal in 2018 and the European election, the EU has delivered the European Green Deal (GD) including several initiatives, notably the Biodiversity Strategy, the Farm to Fork strategy, Soil and Forest Strategy and the Climate Adaptation plan. The different initiatives set up ambitious sustainability targets to be achieved mostly by 2030, to which the new CAP is expected to contribute to. The changes introduced by the NDM in view of the achievement of the EU sustainability ambitions, pose new challenges to the CAP governance, which can be identified as follows: Transfer of responsibility from the EC to MSs; Shift from a compliance-based to a performance-based evaluation system; Increased sustainability ambition.

Objectives, methodology and data

The overall ambition of Tools4CAP is to support the design, monitoring and evaluation of the CAP-Strategic Plans (SP) by stimulating MSs to adopt methods and tools tailored to their needs.

The project has five specific objectives:

- To provide a shared knowledge base and evaluation of current methods and tools for the design and implementation of the SP;
- To identify and adapt innovative methods and tools by taking stock of relevant and replicable solutions developed in recent and ongoing research projects and other EU initiatives;

- To empower end users and policymakers to adopt innovative methods and tools for the SP design and monitoring by providing them with methodological guidance to best solutions' choice, implementation and good practices;
- To establish a replication lab supporting the practical demonstration and uptake of innovative solutions by operationalizing and testing methods and tools across case studies;
- To set up a capacity building hub to mobilize knowledge and transfer operational capabilities to end users by enabling mutual learning, participation and science-policy dialogue.

Results (expected)

The governance of the SP, therefore, begins with their design, and continues across their implementation. Figure 1 synthetizes the key steps of the design and implementation processes.

Figure 1. Understanding of the Strategic Plan design and implementation steps
Source: Tools4CAP Project

The results expected (10) are listed below:

- 1)Tool4CAP will build a comprehensive and open-access inventory of methods and tools used across EU-27 and relevant international examples;
- 2)Tool4CAP will formulate an in-depth understanding of the NDM, its keystones, principles and legal requirements, and evaluate the collected methods and tools accordingly, to cast light on potential and limitations of existing methods and tools, and identify and widely share good practices to be replicated across the EU;
- 3)Tool4CAP assesses the challenges and barriers to the adoption of innovative solutions across MSs, as well as country and end users' needs, according to three key areas, namely: modelling and forecasting tools, innovative and participatory decision tools, and novel data sources and monitoring technologies;
- 4)According to the defined needs and challenges, suitable innovative methods and tools are identified and adapted for the three key areas;

- 5) Tool4CAP will produce methodological guidelines for the implementation of innovative methods and tools adapted to MSs' needs according to the three key areas: modelling and forecasting tools, innovative and participatory decision tools, and novel data sources and monitoring technologies;
- 6) Tool4CAP will also produce a Handbook for the guidance of MSs and end users to the choice of best solutions and the application of good practices, based on the case studies' experiences, the inventory and evaluation of existing methods and tools;
- 7) Tool4CAP will support the implementation of at least 11 innovative solutions in as many MSs, including at least 2 innovative macro-modelling tools, 4 novel data and monitoring solutions, 3 innovative and participatory decision tools, and 2 integral demonstrations covering modelling, monitoring and participatory decision tools;
- 8) The outputs of the implemented case studies will be showcased through the Tool4CAP Academy in EU level workshops, and discussed through Multi-stakeholder focus groups to promote the adjustment and replication of innovative solutions;
- 9) Tool4CAP will set up a stakeholder engagement platform to ensure the participation of end users, policymakers, and multiple stakeholders for dissemination and to guarantee that the support action is tailored on country and end user's needs. The stakeholder engagement platform will consist of two-rounds National and EU multi-stakeholder focus groups, but it will also rely on the final project conference;
- 10) Besides, the support action will rely on the Tool4CAP Academy consisting of online EU level workshops to disseminate, showcase and train end users to the choice and operationalization of innovative solutions and good practices.

Figure 2 shows the entire activities of the project.

Figure 2. Overall methodology scheme, including work packages and main results of Tool4CAP

Source: Tools4CAP Project

Conclusions

The project will rely on a flexible approach to involve all relevant actors and end users while tailoring its targets to specific country needs. Alongside the development of the understanding of the NDM and the project conceptualization, a detailed picture of the diversity of governance models and actors involved across the EU will be drawn. Through the use of multiple participatory instruments like the stakeholder engagement platform and the Tool4CAP Academy, the project will remain flexible in the identification and engagement of those actors that are relevant to inform specific tasks and disseminate outputs.

Tool4CAP aspires to set in motion a double support action to: 1) support the implementation of the SP in the period 2023-2027 with most advanced data and technological solutions for monitoring and evaluation; and 2) support the design of the next-generation SP, which will likely take place during the last phases of the implementation period 2023-2027, with cutting edge modelling tools and innovative participatory decision-making approaches. To this end, Tool4CAP will provide timely support to MS's needs by implementing different support actions at subsequent stages of the CAP 2023-2027 period.

Literature

Tools4CAP Project Application